

PIACERE

Deliverable D2.3

PIACERE DevSecOps Framework - v1

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Abstract:	This deliverable will integrate all the components developed by the other technical WPs in the PIACERE DevSecOps Framework. Different versions of the PIACERE DevSecOps Framework will be provided following an incremental approach. The first version will be an initial prototype with the core functionalities implemented; the second version will augment these functionalities taking into consideration the feedback coming for the use cases and the final version will include corrections and feedback coming from the implementation of the use cases. The software will be accompanied by a Technical Specification Report. When appropriate, the architecture definition of the DevSecOps framework will be updated
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Terms and abbreviations

BPMN	Business Process Model and Notation
CD	Continuous Delivery
CI	Continuous Integration
CRUD	Create, Read, Update, Delete
CSEP	Canary Sandbox Environment Provisioner, component of PIACERE WP5
CSP	Cloud Service Provider
DevOps	Development and Operations
DevSecOps	Development, Security and Operations
DMC	DOML Model Checker
DMN	Decision Model and Notation
DoA	Description of Action
DOML	DevSecOps Modelling Language, as provided by PIACERE WP3
DMC	DOML Model Checker
EC	European Commission
GA	Grant Agreement to the project
IaC	Infrastructure as Code
ICG	Infrastructural Code Generator, component of PIACERE WP3
IDE	Integrated Development Environment, component of PIACERE WP3
IEC	Infrastructural Elements Catalogue, component of PIACERE WP5
IEM	IaC Execution Manager, component of PIACERE WP5
IOP	IaC Optimization Platform, component of PIACERE WP5
ISR	IaC Scan Runner
KR	Key Result
KR13	Key Result 13 – PIACERE DevSecOps framework – the integration key result that is presented in this deliverable
MC	Monitoring Controller
PM	Performance Monitoring
PMC	Performance Monitoring Controller
PRC	PIACERE Runtime Controller
PSL	Performance Self-Learning
SH	Self-Healing
SM	Security Monitoring
SSL	Security Self-Learning
SW	Software
TSR	Technical Specification Report (e.g., this document)

Executive Summary

This document describes the integration of the PIACERE framework v1 as a whole (Key Result 13 [KR13] v1) and acts as the Technical Specification Report (TSR) for the integrated PIACERE framework and the reported new software – PIACERE Runtime Controller (PRC), also in v1. The PRC orchestrates the runtime of the PIACERE framework. The integration options of the IDE are also discussed as the IDE is the central point of PIACERE framework at design time.

The work reported here has been done as part of Task 2.3 (T2.3) in Work Package 2 (WP2) but it involves all other technical WPs, that is WP3, WP4, WP5, and WP6, as they provide the tools that compose the PIACERE framework. The PRC interacts with tools of the PIACERE runtime, i.e., those from WP5 and WP6.

The document starts with introduction to the contents. Next, it presents an explanation of the scope of integration, as this lays the ground for the rest of the document. Then, it moves onto the description of integration points considered in this integration work which describe how the integration was conducted. After that, sections on the PRC implementation and usage are included which put the PRC in context and describe it in detail. Finally, a conclusions section and appendix on Camunda (which is an important part of the current implementation of the PRC) close the document.

The main result of this deliverable is the integrated PIACERE framework and the PRC. Together they allow the PIACERE user to reap the benefits of all the PIACERE tooling provided in the first year (i.e., by month 12) of the project and showcase that the PIACERE-provided tools can be used together.

Next versions of this deliverable (v2, due month 27, and v3, due month 33) will base off this v1, updating it to adjust to changes made in the integrated components and possibly polishing the integration details.

1 Introduction

1.1 About this deliverable

This document contains the details of integration of the PIACERE framework v1 as a whole (KR13 v1) and is the TSR for it and the PRC v1. The integration involves all tools produced as part of other technical WPs, i.e., from WP3 to WP6. The PRC orchestrates the runtime and interacts with runtime tools from WP5 and WP6. The goal of this deliverable is to put the technical results in context and present their details as well as their usage.

This document does not concern itself with internal integration of components inside their respective deliverables as is the case with WP6 tooling as well as parts of other WPs.

1.2 Document structure

The document is comprised of 8 sections split into subsections. The 1st section is this introduction. The 2nd section describes the scope of integration. The 3rd section goes into detail on the integration points. The 4th section introduces PRC's architecture and technical aspects. The 5th section describes the usage side of PRC. The 6th section offers conclusion. The 7th section contains references. Finally, the 8th section is an appendix on Camunda [1].

2 Scope of integration

This section lays the ground for understanding the integration of the PIACERE DevSecOps framework, also called PIACERE framework or simply PIACERE. The scope is described here along with main points of integration.

2.1 Components used in the integration of v1

In the first version of the PIACERE framework, the components used for integration are all those available at month 12 of the project. They are summarised, along with the respective Key Results and Deliverables in the table below (Table 1).

Table 1 PIACERE Framework v1 components

Key Results	Deliverable	Component name
KR13	D2.3 (this one)	PIACERE Runtime Controller (PRC)
KR3	D3.4	Infrastructural Code Generator (ICG)
KR2	D3.7	Integrated Development Environment (IDE)
KR5	D4.1	DOML Model Checker (DMC)
KR6, KR7	D4.4	IaC Scan Runner (ISR)
KR10	D5.1	IaC Execution Manager (IEM)
KR8	D5.4	Canary Sandbox Environment Provisioner (CSEP)
KR9	D5.7	IaC Optimization Platform (IOP)
KR9	D5.7	Infrastructural Elements Catalogue (IEC)
KR11, KR12	D6.1	Monitoring Controller (MC)
KR11	D6.1	Performance Monitoring Controller (PMC)
KR11	D6.1	Performance Self-Learning (PSL)
KR11	D6.1	Self-Healing (SH)
KR11, KR12	D6.1	Security Monitoring and Self-Learning (SM&SSL)

All components used for the integration described in this deliverable (except the IDE, due to its different nature) have their interfaces follow the popular REST API practice and are described in the OpenAPI [2] format. Certain details on interfaces and the interaction with them are described in section 3. The IDE is a desktop component and thus does not offer REST API.

Additionally, an external, helper component is used in v1 integration – Gitea [3] – serving as the DOML & IaC Repository. In practice, any Git repository hosting solution is a viable replacement.

2.2 Deviations from the planned workflow

The planned workflow for PIACERE framework v1 was reported in [D2.1](#). However, it has been noticed that there are missing functionalities in delivered components, making it impossible to deliver certain aspects of the workflow. The table below (Table 2) reports the deviations from the planned workflow.

Table 2 Deviations from the planned workflow (adapted from D2.1)

Arrow	From	To	Description	Deviation
17	Infrastructural Elements Catalogue (IEC)	PIACERE Runtime Controller (PRC)	PRC gets (and saves) info from/to the catalogue.	There is no use for this interaction.

Arrow	From	To	Description	Deviation
21	IaC Execution Manager (IEM)	Integrated Development Environment (IDE)	IEM returns feedback to IDE.	PRC remains the sole contact between the design time (IDE) and runtime tools. The feedback, therefore, comes from PRC.
31	Security Monitoring (SM)	Infrastructural Elements Catalogue (IEC)	Adds security related information to the infrastructure elements to support IOP algorithms.	Omitted because it is currently not possible to store this data.
32	Performance Monitoring (PM)	Infrastructural Elements Catalogue (IEC)	Adds performance related information to the infrastructure elements to support IOP algorithms.	Omitted because it is currently not possible to store this data.
33	IaC Optimization Platform (IOP)	DOML & IaC Repository	IOP gets/saves info from/to catalogue.	PRC gets this info for IOP and there is no saving it back.
36	PIACERE Runtime Controller (PRC)	Infrastructural Elements Catalogue (IEC)	PRC saves info to the catalogue.	Omitted because it is currently not possible to store this data.

The reported missing functionalities were postponed for year 2 version of components, that is the integration of PIACERE framework v2.

Additionally, we have evaluated the possibility of calling the IOP from the IDE. This is described in detail in Section 3.3.

2.3 Main points of integration

This section describes the two main points of integration in the PIACERE workflow – the IDE and the PRC (PIACERE Runtime Controller). The latter’s details are reported in this deliverable.

2.3.1 IDE: Design time to runtime

One of the pivotal tools of the PIACERE project is the IDE – being a Graphical User Interface (GUI) of the PIACERE framework, it supports the design time of the PIACERE Framework and is a gateway to the runtime. Several other Key Results (KRs) of the project are integrated with the IDE using one of integration mechanisms that IDE and these technologies commonly provide. The PIACERE IDE is customized with suitable plug-ins that integrate with the different tools, in order to minimize the learning curve and to simplify adoption of the PIACERE DevSecOps IaC approach. Different tools may be integrated in different ways. The best ways are currently being continuously evaluated and the first implementations are under way.

The PIACERE tools integrated with the IDE can be grouped into two types. Design-time tools, which allow designing/defining the solution to be deployed, and runtime tools, which try to implement the designed system. Depending on the type of tools, the integration may be more or less tightly coupled, with design-time tools being the candidates for a tighter integration.

To integrate the tools with the IDE (Figure 1), a set of menus is enabled to facilitate access. Some of these tools could be fully integrated into Eclipse and should be developed as Eclipse plugins. On the other hand, other tools could be run in isolation and invoked through a REST API.

Figure 1 PIACERE IDE integration options

Several integration patterns, focusing on the Eclipse plugin architecture, are available. The proposed ones are:

1. **Native Extension/plugin.** With this option, the tool will be integrated as an Eclipse plugin and will be embedded into the PIACERE IDE:

Figure 2 Eclipse Plugin - Integration mechanism

2. **External Service: Backend Service.** This option allows to integrate an external Tool Service which could receive (for example, through a REST API) a DOML model ([D3.1](#)) and any necessary configuration to perform some task, e.g., storing its results in a repository.

Figure 3 External Service: Backend Service

3. **External Service: Interactive Service.** In this case, the external Tool Service provides a response to the PIACERE IDE (either directly or via a callback) with some tool-generated resources that can then be retrieved and stored by the IDE.

Figure 4 Interactive Service

4. **External Service: Interactive Service with visual (Editor/Viewer) feedback.** This final case is an extension of the previous one where it is required to provide some kind of Eclipse extension to visualize or to manage/edit tool-generated resources.

Figure 5 Interactive Service with visual feedback

2.3.2 PRC: Control of the runtime

The other pivotal tool of the PIACERE project is the PRC – PIACERE Runtime Controller – which orchestrates the runtime part of the PIACERE framework and is a bridge for the IDE to go from design time to runtime. Various runtime components are interacted with and interact with the PRC. The details of PRC are reported in this deliverable in sections 4 and 5. This section is kept short for structure.

2.4 Delivery of the integrated components

All components from Table 1 were used in the integration. The components were developed concurrently, and their code history was tracked using the Git version control system. The **y1** branch tracks the progress for year 1 of the PIACERE project. All components, except the IDE (due to its desktop nature), are containerised and were co-deployed on the project-internal integration server under the control of Docker [4]. Each component offers its Dockerfile recipes and builds and publishes its images to project-internal Artifactory-backed [5] Docker images registry. GitLab [6] CI/CD (Continuous Integration / Continuous Delivery) coordinates this process.

The docker-compose [7] recipes are available for easy recreation of the integration environment. Each component has a dedicated docker-compose file specifying its subcomponents and an internal network which co-hosts them. All REST API endpoints are exposed on a common network to allow for communication between the components. Access multiplexing is done with Traefik [8]. The environment preparation and PIACERE framework installation is done using Ansible [9] playbooks.

2.5 Status of the integration

In the following table, the status of the integration is reported (Table 3). Integrations with IDE are all under development due to a delay in IDE delivery. This delay was caused by the change of technology (From Eclipse Theia to Eclipse Desktop) due to the immaturity of Eclipse Theia with ecore technologies and Theia's incomplete technical documentation on installation.

Table 3 Integration status

Invoker	Invoked	Status	Comment
IDE	IEC	In development	
IDE	DMC	In development	
IDE	IOP	In development	
IDE	ICG	In development	
IDE	ISR	In development	
IDE	CSEP	In development	
IDE	PRC	In development	
IDE	Monitoring Dashboard	In development	
PRC	IEM	Implemented	
PRC	MC	Implemented	
PRC	IOP	Implemented	
IOP	IEC	Implemented	
MC	PMC	Implemented	
MC	PSL	Implemented	
MC	SH	Implemented	
SH	PRC	In development	The PRC is delivered with this deliverable and, thus, the integration with it is in progress.

3 Integration implementation

This section describes the implementations of integration points – between main integration points and the other tools that are invoked or invoke the main integration points. The order of the components in section names is: invoker – invoked. The invoked component is described in the context of being invoked by the invoker.

3.1 IDE – IEC

The Infrastructural Elements Catalogue (IEC) stores information about the services available at service providers, as well as the instances of each of these services deployed by the PIACERE infrastructure.

Expected behaviour

The IEC receives information from different sources. What we have called “static information”, concerns the available services provided by the CSPs and other service offering providers. This information is provided through the IDE and can be later retrieved.

Input

During design time, the IEC frontend is used to introduce information about services, the introduced information is stored in a database that is finally exported into an SQL script. This script will be used to provide the initial set of information into the IEC once it is deployed into the pilots or the different environments. Below we include an example of an SQL statement to insert a service:

```
INSERT INTO iecbackend.root_service
(service_name,created_date,last_modified_date,deleted_date,service_class_id) VALUES
('C1_Spain','2020-04-01 17:46:19','2020-04-01 17:46:19',NULL,3);
INSERT INTO iecbackend.service_attribute_type
(name,nfr_name,is_enumeration,is_form,is_common,is_functional_requirement,parent_id
,child_id,units,unit_factor,unit_rule,eval_rule,created_date,last_modified_date,del
eted_date) VALUES
('Region','Region',1,0,1,0,NULL,2,'','','LIKE','','2021-04-01
17:46:19','2021-04-01 17:46:19',NULL),
('Zone','Zone',1,0,1,0,1,NULL,'','','LIKE','','2021-04-01 17:46:19','2021-04-
01 17:46:19',NULL),
('Provider','Provider',1,0,1,0,NULL,NULL,'','','LIKE','','2021-04-01
17:46:19','2021-04-01 17:46:19',NULL),
('Virtual CPU Cores','','0,0,0,1,NULL,NULL,'','','>=','variable > 0','2021-04-
01 17:46:19','2021-04-01 17:46:19',NULL),
('Frequency per Core','','0,0,0,1,NULL,NULL,'MHz','1','>=','variable >
0','2021-04-01 17:46:19','2021-04-01 17:46:19',NULL),
('Memory','','0,0,0,1,NULL,NULL,'MB,GB,TB','1048576,1024,1','>=','variable >
0','2021-04-01 17:46:19','2021-04-01 17:46:19',NULL),
('Instance
Storage','','0,0,0,1,NULL,NULL,'MB,GB,TB','1048576,1024,1','>=','variable > 0','2021-
04-01 17:46:19','2021-04-01 17:46:19',NULL),
('Optimized
for','','1,0,0,1,NULL,NULL,'','','LIKE','','2021-04-01
17:46:19','2021-04-01 17:46:19',NULL),
('Public
IP','','1,0,0,1,NULL,NULL,'','','LIKE','','2021-04-01
17:46:19','2021-04-01 17:46:19',NULL),
('Underpinning
Technology','','0,0,0,1,NULL,NULL,'','','LIKE','','2021-04-01
17:46:19','2021-04-01 17:46:19',NULL);
INSERT INTO iecbackend.service_attribute_value
(service_attribute_value,unit_value,check_list_value,created_date,last_modified_dat
e,deleted_date,service_attribute_type_id,root_service_id) VALUES
('00EU','','','2021-04-01 17:46:20','2021-04-01 17:46:20',NULL,1,1),
('SPEU','','','2021-04-01 17:46:20','2021-04-01 17:46:20',NULL,2,1),
('ARSY','','','2021-04-01 17:46:20','2021-04-01 17:46:20',NULL,3,1),
```

```
( '1', '', '', '2021-04-01 17:46:20', '2021-04-01 17:46:20', NULL, 4, 1),
( '1500', '', '', '2021-04-01 17:46:20', '2021-04-01 17:46:20', NULL, 5, 1),
( '1', 'GB', '', '2021-04-01 17:46:20', '2021-04-01 17:46:20', NULL, 6, 1),
( '40', 'GB', '', '2021-04-01 17:46:20', '2021-04-01 17:46:20', NULL, 7, 1),
( '', '', '', '2021-04-01 17:46:20', '2021-04-01 17:46:20', NULL, 8, 1),
( '', '', '', '2021-04-01 17:46:20', '2021-04-01 17:46:20', NULL, 9, 1),
( 'VmWare', '', '', '2021-04-01 17:46:20', '2021-04-01 17:46:20', NULL, 10, 1);
```

Besides that, the IEC exposes a Web user interface and an API that allows to extend this initial list to adapt to the use cases needs and evolution. The Web user interface enables the create, read, update and delete (CRUD) capabilities for several entities: Services, service classes and instances (Figure 6).

The screenshot shows the Piacere IEC v0.0.1-SNAPSHOT web interface. The navigation menu includes Home, Services, Service Classes, Instances, Administration, Language, and Account. The main content area displays a welcome message and a table of service counts across different providers.

	AIMES	Amazon	Arsys	Azure	Google	CloudSigma
Database	0 service(s)	4 service(s)	0 service(s)	2 service(s)	2 service(s)	0 service(s)
Storage	0 service(s)	2 service(s)	4 service(s)	3 service(s)	2 service(s)	0 service(s)
Virtual Machine	0 service(s)	11 service(s)	9 service(s)	6 service(s)	2 service(s)	1 service(s)

Additional information at the bottom of the interface includes a European Union funding notice, the Tecnalia logo, and a copyright notice for 2021.

Figure 6 IEC web interface

The Web user interface is the main integration point for the IDE.

The IEC also has a REST API that can be accessed IDE for automation purposes. This REST API can be explored and tested through the IEC web interface.

Currently, we include only one method that could be offered to the IDE for some automation – GET /api/root-service/catalogue – that returns all the services present in the IEC (Figure 7).

root-service-resource Root Service Resource

GET /api/root-services/catalogue `getAllRootServicesCatalogue`

Parameters

Name	Description
serviceClassId.equals integer(\$int64) (query)	<input type="text" value="serviceClassId.equals"/>
serviceClassId.greaterThan integer(\$int64) (query)	<input type="text" value="serviceClassId.greaterThan"/>
serviceClassId.greaterThanOrEqualTo integer(\$int64) (query)	<input type="text" value="serviceClassId.greaterThanOrEqualTo"/>
serviceClassId.in array[integer] (query)	<input type="button" value="Add integer item"/>
serviceClassId.lessThan	<input type="text"/>

Figure 7 IEC REST API

Output

The expected output for the IDE will be the web user interface. From there we expect that several elements may be used in the DOML model development: Services, service classes and even instances.

3.2 IDE – DOML Model Checker

The DOML Model Checker (DMC) is a tool that statically analyzes IaC for compliance with a pre-defined or user-supplied specification. It reports to the user whether the specification is satisfied or not.

Expected behaviour

The user requests the verification of the currently displayed DOML model in the IDE through an appropriate user interaction (e.g., a button or menu entry). Then, the IDE sends to the DMC a model checking request containing the DOML model. The DMC then processes the IaC and sends the outcome of the model checking back to the IDE. Finally, the IDE displays the verification outcome to the user.

The interaction between the IDE and the DMC is performed through REST APIs. The REST API enables the interaction by providing one single endpoint (`/modelcheck`), which accepts a POST request containing the elements listed in the Input section. The result (described in the Output section) of the model checking process is then sent to the client as the answer to its POST request (Figure 8).

Figure 8 DMC REST API

Input

The DMC receives from the IDE a verification request containing:

- The DOML model to be verified in a machine-readable format, possibly XML (**required**),
- A string describing the requirement to be verified (**optional**, currently not supported).

Output

The DMC answers with:

- A string stating the verification outcome (**required**). This can be either “sat”, meaning the model satisfies the requirements, “unsat”, meaning the model does not satisfy the requirements, or “dontknow”, meaning the model checking process was inconclusive due to a timeout.
- A string describing the issue(s) found in the model (**optional**, set if there are issues).

3.3 IDE – IOP

The IaC Optimization Platform is a tool for optimizing the IaC based on the constraints in the DOML model.

Expected behaviour

In a nutshell, the IOP is responsible for finding the best possible infrastructure combination given the input data received. In other words, the optimizer uses an optimization algorithm to find an optimized deployment configuration of the IaC on the appropriate infrastructural elements that best meet the predefined constraints, i.e., are optimal. This information is supposed to be presented to the PIACERE user.

The IOP offers an embedded Swagger UI (Figure 9) to facilitate the understanding and usage by the IDE.

Figure 9 Swagger UI page for IOP

Input

In this preliminary phase, the input data is accepted in JSON, but in the future it will be accepted in the DOML format. The input that the IOP receives has currently the following format:

```
{
  "Call": [{
    "Objectives": [
      "cost",
      "availability",
      "performance"
    ],
    "Requirements": {
      "cost": 200.0,
      "availability": 98.0,
      "region": "00EU"
    }
  }]
}
```

In the example the objectives to optimize are three: *i*) cost, *ii*) availability and *iii*) performance; while the requirements are also three: *i*) the total cost of the solution must be less than 200, *ii*) the availability must be, at least, 98 and *iii*) the region of all the elements must be Europe.

Output

Once the IOP completes the optimization, it returns as output a String, also in JSON format, which is a list of found solutions. This is an example with two solutions:

```
{
  "Solutions":[
    {
      "Objectives":[
        200.0,
        99.76666666666665,
        8.0
      ],
      "Solution":"[Storage4_Europe, db.dynamo.3, C8_Germany]"
    },
    {
      "Objectives":[
        145.53,
        98.03333333333335,
        11.0
      ],
      "Solution":"[Storage1_Spain, db.dynamo.3, t2.nano]"
    }
  ]
}
```

Basically, for each solution, the objectives (for example, cost: 200, availability: 99.7 and performance: 8), and the solution itself (that is, the elements of the IEC that have been chosen) are shown.

3.4 IDE – ICG

The Infrastructural Code Generator (ICG) is the PIACERE component that allows generating executable infrastructural code (IaC) from models written in DOML.

Expected behaviour

The interface of the ICG is through a REST API (Figure 10). If the conversion of a DOML model in IaC code is required, the ICG expects a POST call from the IDE containing the model with all the necessary data. After the ICG has generated all the IaC files they will be sent back as a response (compressed in a zip or tar package).

Figure 10 ICG REST API

The ICG also provides logs related to the process of generation of the IaC files, containing errors, warnings and info useful to the end user. These logs need to be exported to the user in a way that is easily readable and comprehensible.

Lastly, the ICG uses configuration files on the local filesystem that allow the extensibility of the tool through the definition of the components and templates, which are going to be expanded when new components are added. To update these files, the filesystem can be mounted from an external source where the IDE can access them.

Inputs

The input of the ICG is the DOML model.

Outputs

The output of the ICG is a compressed package (zip or tar) containing the IaC files.

3.5 IDE – IaC Scan Runner

The IaC Scan Runner is a component providing a single interface to the functionalities of IaC Security Inspector and Component Security Inspector. This component includes multiple IaC and component checks that are used to perform scanning of IaC and returning the discovered common security vulnerabilities and misconfigurations.

Expected behaviour

IaC Scan Runner is usually set up in a Docker container and gets exposed as a REST API service that comes with an OpenAPI Specification that allows users to interact with the API through browser (Figure 11). Using the `/checks` endpoint, the API enables the user to list and filter the supported checks (those are described thoroughly within IaC Scanner documentation: <https://xlab-si.github.io/iac-scanner-docs/>). Apart from IaC and component distinctions, checks can also be local (executing on the machine where the IaC Scan Runner is running) or remote (executing partially or wholly on the remote service, e.g., Snyk, SonarCloud, etc.). Checks can be enabled (using `/enable` endpoint) or disabled (using `/disable` endpoint) for running. Some of them are disabled by default and need to be configured (via `/configure` endpoint by supplying necessary configuration files or/and credentials) before running. The main API endpoint is `/scan`, which expects the compressed IaC file and a list of checks to be executed while scanning (if no list is supplied, the API runs all enabled checks) [D4.4].

default	
GET	<code>/checks</code> Retrieve and filter checks
PATCH	<code>/checks/{check_name}/enable</code> Enable check for running
PATCH	<code>/checks/{check_name}/disable</code> Disable check for running
PATCH	<code>/checks/{check_name}/configure</code> Configure check
POST	<code>/scan</code> Initiate IaC scan

Figure 11 Section from Swagger UI page for IaC Scan Runner REST API

```

Curl
curl -X 'GET' \
  'https://scanner.xopera.piacere.esilab.org/iac-scan-runner/checks?keyword=terraform' \
  -H 'accept: application/json'

Request URL
https://scanner.xopera.piacere.esilab.org/iac-scan-runner/checks?keyword=terraform

Server response
Code    Details
200
Response body
[
  {
    "name": "tfLint",
    "description": "A Pluggable Terraform Linter",
    "enabled": true,
    "configured": true,
    "target_entity_type": "IaC"
  },
  {
    "name": "tfsec",
    "description": "Security scanner for your Terraform code",
    "enabled": true,
    "configured": true,
    "target_entity_type": "IaC"
  },
  {
    "name": "terrascan",
    "description": "Terrascan is a static code analyzer for IaC (defaults to scanning Terraform)",
    "enabled": true,
    "configured": true,
    "target_entity_type": "IaC"
  }
]

```

Figure 12 Filtering out check for Terraform in the IaC Scan Runner REST API

The IaC scan will be performed from the IDE just after the ICG generates IaC code from the DOML. The idea is that a user would be able to locate the IaC code within the IDE and, from the context menu, send it directly to the IaC Scan Runner Service. The output of the IaC scan runner will be a text that would be retrieved back to the IDE and presented to the user.

Inputs

Input to the IaC Scan Runner is a compressed package (zip or tar), including the IaC code.

Outputs

Output is a text file (JSON or HTML) that includes the content – warnings and messages – that describe the issues in IaC and the return codes from each of the selected checks.

3.6 IDE – CSEP

The Canary Sandbox Environment Provisioner (CSEP) is a tool providing the PIACERE user with the ability to create (provision) Canary Sandbox Environments – OpenStack in the year 1 version.

Expected behaviour

It is expected that the PIACERE user will be able to issue new deployment requests and browse existing deployments from the IDE. The CSEP provides a REST API with endpoints required to facilitate this (Figure 13). The CSEP renders its own API documentation at the `/docs` path which allows the integrator to inspect the API requirements.

GET	/deployments/	Get All Deployments	▼
POST	/deployments/	Post Deployment	▼
GET	/deployments/{deployment_name}	Get Deployment	▼
DELETE	/deployments/{deployment_name}	Delete Deployment	▼

Figure 13 CSEP API endpoints

There is a *dummy* deployment type provided for integrator's convenience which does not require actual target hosts to be available and the integration can be tested at no cost.

Inputs

As the input, the deployment creation API accepts JSON documents describing the details of the requested deployment. Each deployment is identified by its name which is a user-provided string and has to be unique on that instance of CSEP. The creation of deployments is facilitated by the *POST /deployments/* method. The other methods do not require any input.

Outputs

As the output, the API offers JSON documents describing the details of managed deployments.

3.7 IDE – PRC

The PIACERE Runtime Controller (PRC) is the orchestration tool of the PIACERE runtime. It is described in detail in this document in later sections.

Expected behaviour

The IDE uses PRC to control the runtime of PIACERE. The PRC allows to create new deployments and inspect the state of existing ones. The deployments are identified by their identifiers which are mostly free-form names. Please refer to PRC REST API section in this document for details on the behaviour and inputs and outputs.

3.8 IDE – Monitoring Dashboard

The monitoring components allow gathering metrics from the infrastructure resources that have been deployed by PIACERE framework. PIACERE supports two types of monitoring:

- The **Performance Monitoring** component focuses on gathering performance-related measures from the infrastructure resources. The measures are gathered by agents running in the infrastructure resources. Examples of metrics are memory use, disk use, processes, CPU usage, etc.
- The **Security Monitoring** component focuses on gathering security-related measures from the infrastructure resources. The measures are gathered by agents running in the infrastructure resources.

Expected behaviour

When a new IaC is deployed, an extra task is undertaking the deployment of monitoring agents along with the infrastructure, and the configuration of the monitoring components. Then, the

continuous gathering of performance/security metrics can start. These metrics are evaluated against the expected thresholds or SLAs and, if needed, alerts are sent to the Self-Healing component.

The IDE is expected to enable the user to reach the dashboards of the monitoring system. This is done via the Performance Monitoring Controller (PMC) which offers a REST API (Figure 14).

Figure 14 Swagger UI page for PMC

Inputs

In order to retrieve the URL of the created Grafana dashboard for a specific deployment the performance monitoring controller provides a method to get the URL of the Grafana dashboard. The method can be explored and tested from the Swagger UI embedded in the performance monitoring controller, and the response schema can be seen in Figure 15.

Figure 15 PMC – get deployment response

Outputs

The outputs to the IDE are the created Grafana dashboards location. The dashboard is still in design phase but the current draft with one variable is presented in Figure 16.

Figure 16 Grafana monitoring dashboard draft

The output of the Monitoring system is reflected in one or more visual dashboards, where the metrics, thresholds, etc. can be consulted in a graphical/numerical view. At the time of writing, the dashboards are not designed yet, but a graphic or table is expected for each of the metrics gathered like memory, disk, CPU usage or availability. These dashboards are created on the fly, once the information of the deployed infrastructure is available. For this, pre-defined templates or the Grafana API will be used. Grafana dashboards are HTML elements, and will be integrated in the PIACERE IDE, as iframes or a similar technology.

3.9 PRC – IEM

The IEM serves the purpose of deployment and redeployment of IaC. It supports different IaC technologies present in the market and provides a common interface to execute the deployments of the different elements present in the PIACERE project. In addition, the current prototype handles the redeployment and tearing down of existing deployments.

Expected behaviour

The main purpose of the IEM is to handle the lifecycle of the deployments that are managed within the PIACERE framework. The integration between the PRC and the IEM is handled by a REST API. The PRC can perform the following actions this way on the IEM: i) query the status of all active deployments, ii) trigger a deployment, iii) query the status of a particular deployment, and iii) delete a deployment. These actions are depicted in Figure 17 as REST API endpoints.

GET	/deployments/	Read Status	▼
PUT	/deployments/	Deploy	▼
DELETE	/deployments/	Undeploy	▼
GET	/deployments/{deployment_id}	Read Status Deployment	▼

Figure 17 IEM Endpoints

Inputs

The PUT on `/deployments/` triggers or updates a deployment in the infrastructure. The IEM needs a few fields to kick off a deployment, the schema for calling this endpoint is showcased in Figure 18.

```

DeploymentRequest {
  deployment_id*   string
                  title: Deployment Id
  repository*     string
                  title: Repository
  commit*        string
                  title: Commit
  aws_access_key_id string
                  title: Aws Access Key Id
  aws_secret_access_key string
                  title: Aws Secret Access Key
}

```

Figure 18 IEM PUT /deployments/ request schema.

The DELETE /deployments/ serves the purpose of tearing down a particular deployment. In Figure 19, the request body required for the invocation of this endpoint is shown.

```

DeleteDeploymentRequest {
  deployment_id*   string
                  title: Deployment Id
  aws_access_key_id string
                  title: Aws Access Key Id
  aws_secret_access_key string
                  title: Aws Secret Access Key
}

```

Figure 19 IEM DELETE /deployments/ request schema

Outputs

The output is present for GET /deployments/{deployment_id} and its schema is shown in Figure 20.

```

DeploymentResponse {
  deployment_id*   string
                  title: Deployment Id
  status*         string
                  title: Status
  startDate*      string($date-time)
                  title: Startdate
  updateDate*     string($date-time)
                  title: Updatedate
  metadata*       Metadata > {...}
}

```

Figure 20 IEM GET /deployments/{deployment_id} response schema.

3.10 PRC – Monitoring Controller

The monitoring controller (MC) is a utility component that aims to simplify the configuration of the monitoring, self-learning and self-healing component as PIACERE platform creates, updates and destroys deployments. It also isolates the PRC from changes in those mentioned components.

Expected behaviour

This component is in charge of the activation and deactivation of monitoring activities throughout all the monitoring components: performance monitoring, security monitoring, performance Self-learning and security Self-learning. It exposes a REST API (Figure 21).

It is expected that PRC calls this component when initiating new deployment to configure monitoring for it.

Figure 21 MC OpenAPI rendered in embedded Swagger UI

Inputs

The input is the deployment identifier of the deployment to be monitored.

Outputs

The only output is an acknowledge that the request has been received and it is being processed (that is, starting up monitoring and self-learning components).

3.11 Self-Healing – PRC

The PIACERE Runtime Controller (PRC) is the orchestration tool of the PIACERE runtime. It is described in detail in this document in later sections.

Expected behaviour

The Self-Healing uses PRC to issue self-healing requests on existing deployments should the need arise. The PRC allows this via a dedicated per-deployment endpoint. Each deployment is identified by an identifier which is a mostly free-form name. Self-Healing is able to choose the desired self-healing strategy. Please refer to PRC REST API section in this document for details on the behaviour and inputs and outputs.

4 PRC Implementation

4.1 Functional description

The PRC (PIACERE Runtime Controller) is the heart of the PIACERE runtime integration. It is the main component of the runtime called from the design-time tooling (IDE). It is also the main component coordinating the work of the runtime, i.e., calling the other specific tools delivered as part of the PIACERE framework for the runtime and allowing those tools to call back.

The runtime of PIACERE is responsible for ensuring that the designed infrastructure is deployed, monitored, self-healed, and optimized as expected. To this end, the basic concept in the runtime is deployment. Each deployment is managed individually and can be updated by providing an updated design (specifically, IaC). To align with the current trends, the IaC comes from the git version control system where it is versioned.

There were no PRC-specific requirements collected in D2.1. The PRC satisfies the self-imposed requirements of being usable to realise the designed workflow. These are detailed in the table below (Table 4).

Table 4 Requirements addressed by the PRC

Req ID	Description	Status	Comment
PRC1	PRC to allow to start a new deployment with IEM.	Implemented	
PRC2	PRC to control the process of deployment management with IEM (undeploy, redeploy).	Implemented	
PRC3	PRC to track the status of deployment with IEM.	Implemented	
PRC4	PRC to register the deployment with Monitoring Controller.	Implemented	
PRC5	PRC to allow Self-Healing strategies to be run against the deployment.	Partially implemented	This is marked as “partially implemented” as we expect more strategies to be defined and the current ones to be refined.

The main innovation in PRC v1 is the initial integration of runtime components to create a coherent workflow for deployment, its monitoring, self-healing and optimization.

4.1.1 Fitting into overall PIACERE Architecture

The PRC coordinates the workflow, while the other PIACERE tools themselves – the ones referenced above – are concerned with work details. The PRC is responsible for calling the other tools at relevant times. To this end, it has to communicate with them using the interfaces they offer.

There are 3 tools that are called by the PRC v1:

- IEM (IaC Execution Manager): responsible for executing IaC, called due to creation of a new deployment, update of an existing deployment or in the course of a relevant self-healing strategy,

- IOP (IaC Optimisation Platform): responsible for proposing an optimised deployment design, called in the course of a relevant self-healing strategy,
- MC (Monitoring Controller): responsible for configuring the WP6 monitoring, self-learning and self-healing suite of tools.

There is 1 extra tool that is also used by the PRC and it is the central git repository (DOML & IaC Repository) of the deployment. In v1 this is meant to be used only for obtaining the repository contents, specifically the part relevant for IOP to do its job (propose an optimisation). PRC and other tools assume web (http-based) access to the repository.

PRC v1 itself is called by 2 PIACERE tools:

- IDE (the PIACERE GUI in Eclipse): the IDE is user’s default starting point for interaction with PRC, the initial deployment request will likely originate from it,
- Self-Healing (SH): SH uses PRC to request the chosen self-healing strategy to be applied to the deployment.

The placement of the PRC in the architecture of PIACERE framework and its runtime workflow can be seen in Figure 22 (PRC is in the upper right corner of the “PIACERE Run Time” box). The diagram also depicts the interactions described above.

Figure 22 PIACERE Runtime Workflow Diagram as published in D2.1.

4.2 Technical description

4.2.1 Prototype architecture

The architecture of PRC v1 is shown in Figure 23. The PRC is composed of 3 main components:

- PRC API,
- Camunda Platform,
- PRC Camunda Packages.

They are connected via dedicated interfaces.

Figure 23 PRC Architecture Diagram

4.2.2 Components description

The PRC API component offers the PRC REST API (HTTP) interface that can be used by the external world. This is to be used by other PIACERE tools, such as the IDE and Self-Healing. The interface itself is described in detail in the User Manual section. It connects with the Camunda Platform via Camunda Platform’s own REST API. The purpose of the PRC API is to abstract away the details of Camunda’s API and allow for the replacement of the internals in case such a need arises.

The Camunda Platform is the workhorse of the orchestration – it is a BPMN (Business Process Model and Notation) workflow and DMN (Decision Model and Notation) decision automation platform. A dedicated BPMN workflow has been designed for use in PRC. The Camunda Platform allows action extensibility via, e.g., Java Delegates and this mechanism has been chosen for the implementation of the 3rd component.

The PRC Camunda Packages offer a set of Java Delegates that extend the Camunda Platform to run PRC-specific actions. They are used, e.g., to invoke APIs of other PIACERE components.

4.2.3 Technical specifications

The proposed solution is based on the Camunda Platform – a platform for workflow and decision automation that supports BPMN and DMN standards. The choice of Camunda Platform has already been discussed in D2.1. The Camunda Platform version used is the latest at the time of writing – 7.16.0. The Camunda Platform runs in Java Runtime Environment (JRE). The version of JRE used is the latest version of Java 11.

The PRC Camunda Packages are also written in Java 11. They are compiled using the latest version of Java Development Kit (JDK) 11 and each functional class offers a JavaDelegate interface. The project is managed by Maven (currently at version 3.6.0) and run as a Spring Boot application.

The PRC API is written in Python and tested with Python 3.10, but any modern Python (3.8+) should work as no bleeding-edge features of Python are used. The PRC API uses the FastAPI [10] framework, currently in version 0.73.0. This framework supports Asynchronous Server Gateway Interface (ASGI). ASGI must be understood by the used web server. The one chosen for this project is uvicorn [11], currently in version 0.17.5. FastAPI relies on Python’s type annotations to handle API definition and validation of inputs and outputs. FastAPI also generates OpenAPI specification automatically and allows rendering docs in Swagger UI [12] and Redoc [13]. Finally,

Pydantic [14] is used both indirectly, for the purposes of FastAPI, as well as directly for the management of settings (via environment variables). Pydantic’s version is managed by FastAPI. Pydantic provides additional type annotations and validation of objects.

4.3 PRC workflow in BPMN

This section contains a description of the main PRC flow, modelled as BPMN and implemented with the Camunda Platform. Figure 25 presents the BPMN diagram of the process. The theory of BPMN is not described in this deliverable and we invite readers to approach this intuitively.

Figure 24 BPMN model of PRC

4.3.1.1 Main flow

In short, the idea of the process is to prepare a project and deploy it with IEM, check it in with Monitoring Controller, and then wait for a message to finish the process. In the meantime (usually while waiting for the last message), the process is kept alive, and two self-healing methods can be triggered. Below the flow is explained in detail.

1. Start process

2. Clone and prepare the process

This step is executed without interaction with the user. A repository is cloned to a specified directory, then a checkout to a specified commit is performed.

3. Deploy in IEM

This step is executed without interaction with the user. First, a deploy request is sent to IEM via REST API; then the process starts to actively wait for a deploy to complete by checking the IEM status every 30 seconds. Once finished, the result of the deployment is verified. If the deployment fails, the whole process is finished. Otherwise, the flow progresses to the next step.

4. Wait for the message to finish the deployment

At this step, the process is waiting for a specific message: *FinishTheDeploymentMessage*.

5. Finish event

4.3.1.2 Self-healing subprocesses

Apart from the main flow, the PRC process contains two subprocesses. They are non-interrupting, which means they do not cause the termination of the main process. They can be triggered at any time with an appropriate message, but a typical use case in the PRC is receiving them while the process is on hold, waiting for the finishing message.

1. Self-healing with IEM

Self-healing with IEM subprocess is triggered by an *IEMSelfHealingMessage*. As the name suggests, it communicates with IEM via its REST API to execute the self-healing. Generally, it repeats the step *Deploy with IEM* of the main flow with minor implementation and logging differences.

2. Self-healing with IOP

Self-healing with IOP subprocess is triggered by sending an *IOPSelfHealingMessage*. It is executed by a simple request to IOP via its REST API.

5 PRC Delivery and usage

5.1 Package information

PRCRestApi	The delivered package contains two main catalogs and a number of configuration files. The most important are listed below:
src/main	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • src directory contains the whole backend implementation, i.e., configuration classes which are responsible for running a server with the Camunda Platform, implementation of various workflow elements described in 4.3, and a BPMN diagram of the PRC process, • PRCRestApi directory is a Python project implementing the PRC API layer, containing all files required to build and start the service, • .env file contains environmental variables (e.g., addresses of the external tools), • docker-compose.yml, Dockerfile, and pom.xml are configuration files for Docker and Maven systems.
.env	
.gitignore	
.gitlab-ci.yml	
Dockerfile	
LICENSE	
README.md	
docker-compose.yml	
pom.xml	

Figure 25 PRC package contents

5.2 Installation instructions

The software is containerisable and the recipe is provided along with an example docker-compose deployment. The users are recommended to install a relatively modern Docker (19.03+) and docker-compose (1.29+). Then it is only a matter of running

```
docker-compose up -d
```

to get the software running. Please note that the image might take a while to build before it can be used. The docker-compose command above will start both the Camunda Platform and the PRC API service.

5.3 User Manual

The PRC offers interfaces to allow for integration. These are dedicated to the tools expected to be able to integrate with PRC.

The main assumption is that the user is able to create a process instance which overlooks a particular deployment, allowing to trigger further actions on it. The deployment (process instance) should be identified by a name provided by the user (there could be an additional identifier, but the name has to be easily usable for integration purposes as it is passed in by the tools and passed on to the tools).

IDE actions:

- Creating a deployment
- Getting deployments
- Get details (status) of a deployment
- Update an existing deployment

Self-healing actions:

- Run a specific self-healing strategy on an existing deployment
 - The strategy defines the flow in Camunda
 - For Y1 (M15) integration, we defined two strategies:
 - Calling IEM again
 - Calling IOP

5.3.1 PRC REST API

This section contains a detailed description of PRC REST API. The summary is presented in Figure 26.

GET	/deployments	Get All Deployments
POST	/deployments	Create New Deployment
POST	/deployments/{deployment_id}/self_heal	Trigger Self Healing
POST	/deployments/{deployment_id}/finish	Finish The Deployment
GET	/deployments/{deployment_id}	Get Deployment

Figure 26 A summary of available PRC REST API endpoints

The API revolves around deployments, each identified by unique user-provide **deployment_id**. It can be a number, a name, or a mix of alphanumeric characters and symbols, except for '_' (underscore) and ',' (comma) and characters that could interact with URL syntax – this is a limitation of the Camunda Platform. For simplification, a recommended name is composed of letters and, optionally, numbers and whitespaces.

Below, a list of all exposed endpoints is presented.

- Create a new deployment:

POST /deployments

With a request body:

```
{
  "repository_url": "string",
  "deployment_id": "string",
  "commit_id": "string"
}
```

Where **repository_url** is an address of a git repository with a project to deploy, and **commit_id** is an optional commit identifier to be used instead of the default one.

Possible responses are confirmation with status code 200 or a validation error message with status code 422.

An example of a successful response with status code 200:

```
{
  "message": "Request received"
}
```

- Get a list of all deployments:

GET /deployments

The response is a list (potentially empty) of all deployments.

An example of a successful response with status code 200:

```
[
  {
    "deploymentName": "1"
  },
  {
    "deploymentName": "2"
  }
]
```

- Get a specific deployment:

GET /deployments/{deployment_id}

Possible responses are a deployment description with status code 200 or a resource not found as an error with status code 404.

An example of a successful response with status code 200:

```
{
  "deploymentName": "1"
}
```

- Initiate a self-healing process or optimization process:

POST /deployments/{deployment_id}/self_heal

With request body:

```
{
  "method": "method_name"
}
```

Where **method** is a *redeploy* for initiating the self-healing process with IEM tool or *optimize* for initiating the optimization with IOP tool.

Possible responses are a confirmation with status code 200 or an error message with status code 404 (meaning that `deployment_id` does not exist) or 422 (the **method** parameter is invalid, or the request body is otherwise malformed).

An example of a successful response with status code 200 (both methods):

```
{
  "message": "Request received"
}
```

- Finish the deployment”

POST /deployments/{deployment_id}/finish

Possible responses are a deployment description with status code 200 or an error message with code 404 (meaning the deployment was not found).

An example of a successful response with status code 200:

```
{
  "message": "Request received"
}
```

5.4 Licensing information

The license of PRC is yet to be discussed. In future versions of the deliverable, this will be clarified and reported.

5.5 Download

The code is available for review at Tecnalia’s GitLab, in the private part of the PIACERE project: <https://git.code.tecnalia.com/piacere/private/t23-runtime-controller>

The source code can be provided under request through an email to the address appearing on the website (<https://www.piacere-project.eu/>) in the footer under “Contact Us”.

6 Conclusions

This deliverable has described the integration of the PIACERE framework (KR13) v1 and the crucial component of it at runtime – the PRC – in detail. The context, architecture, implementation, and usage of PRC were all described.

The current integration involves all tools delivered in year 1 of the PIACERE project, that is the KRs of other technical WPs: WP3-WP6. The tools used in the integration were summarised in this document and important integration points described. We have also identified shortcomings of the currently available PIACERE tools and adapted the workflow accordingly.

Future versions of this deliverable will adapt the integration to changes in PIACERE tools, possibly polishing the integration details.

DRAFT

7 References

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8 APPENDIX: Camunda internals

Since the PRC is largely based on the Camunda Platform, this section is meant to explain some concepts related to Camunda.

Camunda offers full orchestration of BPM from design to execution. This section does not intend to repeat Camunda documentation, but rather to be a PRC-centric guide for a quick start in understanding the PRC internals. Therefore, it starts with a brief description of Camunda Modeler, then it presents the Camunda Platform, focusing on the web interface, while only generically introducing the Process Engine, Process Applications, or Container and Spring Boot integrations.

8.1 Camunda Modeler

Camunda Modeler is a standalone open-source solution for designing automated processes, workflows, and decision requirements diagrams, using Business Process Model and Notation (BPMN) and Decision Model and Notation (DMN) standards. Moreover, Camunda Modeler can be used to design Camunda Forms. There is a feature of deploying the model (a new model or a new version of an existing model) directly to a running Camunda Platform instance. The Camunda Modeler interface is presented in Figure 27.

Figure 27 Camunda Modeler

8.2 Camunda Platform

Camunda Platform is a Java-based framework supporting BPMN and DMN. This document focuses on briefly introducing the process and workflow automation with BPMN in order to understand how it is used in PRC.

8.2.1 Camunda Platform web interface applications

Camunda Platform offers a web graphical user interface, consisting of three sections: Admin, Tasklist, and Cockpit. The welcome page is shown in Figure 28.

Figure 28 Camunda web interface: welcome page

Admin is an application dedicated for managing users, groups, and other settings and it will not be discussed in this document.

Tasklist allows working on User Tasks, i.e., tasks that require an interaction with a user, for example by filling some form. Another feature of this one is a possibility to start a new process.

Cockpit is dedicated to monitoring and operations. It contains information about deployed BPMN processes, allows searching through running and ended instances and performing operations on these. User can, for example, find all running instances of a chosen BPMN process and visually track their progress as seen in Figure 29.

Figure 29 Camunda web interface: Cockpit

8.2.2 Camunda Platform internals

The core of Camunda Platform is the Process Engine, a component in which modelled and implemented processes are run.

Task implementation approach. Practically, the substantial elements of the BPMN process are events, flow control elements, and tasks. Tasks can be of various types, e.g., user tasks, service tasks, receive tasks, send tasks and others. These types are BPMN definitions and in PRC user and service tasks are mostly applied. Camunda offers several ways of implementing the various types of tasks:

- Expression – evaluates an expression using expression language (precisely, JUEL). Convenient for small pieces of logic directly in BPMN element.
- Script Task – execute a script inside the engine, can be implemented via various scripting languages (e.g. JavaScript, Groovy). Can be embedded in the BPMN or referenced.
- Java Delegate – calls a named bean or Java class implementing *JavaDelegate* interface. It is executed in the same Java Virtual Machine as Camunda Platform. Convenient for more complicated tasks.
- Connector – uses a configurable connector. REST and SOAP connectors are provided. It is configured directly in BPMN. The idea is that the task is performed by some external API.
- External Task – pulls a service task into an external worker threads and informs process engine of completion. Used for heavy and complex tasks, to introduce scalability, hardware implementation, or to avoid timeouts.

All the types external tasks are using push pattern, which means the process engine actively issues a service call (or script). External tasks use a pull pattern, where external worker threads query the engine (via API), do the actual work and notify the engine about completion.

The PRC uses Java Delegates for all its task implementations.

Interacting with the process. One of the essential notions in the BPMN are events. These elements denote some actions that trigger the flow in BPMN diagram. Events can be start elements or inner elements.

- None Event – used only as a start element if no other more specific event is necessary,
- Message Event – used for routing specific incoming message to a specific and unique process instance,
- Timer Event – for making the process wait for or repeat some action,
- Signal Event – for routing a specific signal to all process instances waiting for it,
- Condition Event – the process instance passes this element only when a specific condition is met

It is worth to highlight that messages and signals can be emitted by implementation of tasks, by a BPMN process or externally. The last approach can be used for interacting with Camunda process, for example by executing a REST call to send a message to a specific process instance or a signal to all process instances.

The PRC uses None Events, Message Events, and Timer Events.

Subprocess. There are a few types of subprocesses in Camunda: embedded subprocess (used rather for grouping than introducing additional possibilities), call activities (similar to the embedded subprocess, but invoking a separate BPMN process), and event subprocess. The last type is used in PRC. They can be implemented as interrupting (all active instances of its scope are terminated, and the control is passed to the subprocess) or non-interrupting (can be called multiple times without terminating other instances in the scope). It is run inside the scope, so it has access to all process variables. PRC uses non-interrupting event subprocesses.

Process Instance. When a user starts the process, they create a **process instance**. At the same time, **multiple process instances** can exist. Each process instance is fully independent and exists in its own scope in Camunda Process Engine.